

Effect of the fatty acid chain length on the efficiency of isosorbide diesters as biobased plasticizers for polylactide

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Abstract

The development of biobased plasticizers has become crucial for enhancing the intrinsic brittleness of poly(lactide) (PLA). This work reports on the effect of the fatty acid chain-length on the plasticization efficiency of their isosorbide diesters, namely isosorbide dibutyrate (IDB), isosorbide dicaprylate (IDC), and isosorbide dipalmitate (IDP), as plasticizers for PLA. The plasticizers were synthesized through esterification of isosorbide with fatty acids of varying chain-length, namely butyric acid (C4), caprylic acid (C8), and palmitic acid (C16). The miscibility of the synthesized plasticizers and PLA was theoretically assessed by calculating their solubility parameters, and experimentally through mechanical, thermal, and morphological characterization. Results show that isosorbide esters with short-chain (C4), and medium-chain (C8) fatty acids, significantly enhanced PLA toughness and ductile properties, reducing the glass transition temperature (T_g) in a remarkable way, with a subsequent dramatic increase in elongation

at break. In contrast, isosorbide esters with long-chain (C8) fatty acids exhibited limited miscibility, leading to partial phase separation but still improving the impact strength and overall ductile properties. Additionally, all formulations showed exceptional disintegration rates in controlled compost soil, highlighting their potential as “double-green” plasticizers for PLA, expanding the potential industrial applications of PLA with improved toughness.

Keywords: isosorbide; esterification, fatty acids; poly(lactide); toughness; plasticization

1. Introduction.

In recent years, there has been an increase in social awareness regarding environmental issues and sustainable development. Within this dynamic new paradigm, the development of biopolymers has gained significant importance and will play a crucial role in achieving various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined in the United Nations' 2023 agenda [1]. Among the most notable developments in the field of biopolymers, those from renewable resources and biodegradable have found high interest. This group includes polysaccharides (starch, cellulose, pectin, chitin, among others) [2, 3], proteins (soybean, gluten, zein, and so on) [4, 5], and aliphatic polyesters obtained through bacterial fermentation, such as poly(hydroxyalkanoates) (PHA) [6, 7]. Despite these advancements, poly(lactide) or poly(lactic acid) (PLA) remains one of the most attractive options at an industrial level [8], with its usage extending across sectors such as biomedical [9], automotive [10], electrical/electronic [11], furniture, and primarily in the packaging industry [12]. PLA is generally obtained through ring-opening polymerization (ROP) of lactide, which is derived from the fermentation of starch-rich compounds. The general properties of PLA include competitive cost, balanced properties, biodegradability, and processing capabilities like many commodity plastics. However, it is an intrinsically brittle polymer with a low elongation at break (usually less than 10%), resulting in low toughness [13, 14].

There are several strategies to overcome or at least minimize this drawback. Copolymerization of lactic acid with other flexible monomers such as caprolactone, glycolide, ethylene glycol, vinyl alcohol, among others, is an interesting approach, but this is not yet a cost-effective technology and consequently, it is not widely used on an industrial scale. The physical

blending of PLA with flexible polymers such as poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) [15], poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) [16], poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate (PBAT) [17], poly(propylene carbonate) (PPC) [18], is another feasible and easy to be carried out approach, even at industrial scale. However, this often results in immiscibility/incompatibility phenomena between polymers, which restricts the ductile properties of the blends. Finally, plasticization is a technically and economically viable alternative to improve the ductile properties of PLA. To achieve best results, plasticizers must exhibit good miscibility with the bulk PLA (even upon long-term storage), low volatility, non-toxicity, and should not compromise the biodegradability of PLA. A wide range of monomeric and polymeric plasticizers have been proposed to enhance the ductile properties of PLA. While monomeric plasticizers, such as citrate esters [19], adipates [20], cinnamates [21], tartrates [22], lactates [23], terpenoids [24], vegetable oils and glycerides [25, 26], among others, offer greater compatibility and improved ductile properties, they exhibit some volatility and a tendency to migrate over time, leading to aging. On the other hand, oligomeric/polymeric plasticizers such as poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) [27], poly(propylene glycol) (PPG) [28], oligomers of lactic acid (OLA) [29], often offer limited miscibility, depending on the molecular weight [30], which affects the final performance. However, they provide greater resistance to migration and aging [31]. Thus, PLA plasticization it is still a challenge, since most of these plasticizers show low thermal stability, easy migration, or poor plasticization properties [32].

Isosorbide (1,4:3,6-dianhydro-D-glucitol) is a bicyclic compound that is currently obtained at industrial scale by the hydrogenation of glucose, which gives sorbitol. Subsequent double dehydration leads to obtaining isosorbide [33], which is a biobased diol with increasing applications in the field of pharmaceutical industry, as surfactant, polymer plasticization, catalysis, among other uses [34]. It is a non-toxic, biodegradable, chiral and rigid molecule with a particular chemical structure including two hydroxyl groups, and it has been proposed as a biobased building block for the polymer industry [35]. Moreover, the intrinsic structure of isosorbide diesters makes them compatible with poly(vinyl) chloride (PVC), being able to act as biobased and biodegradable plasticizers.. Furthermore, they show a similar structure to common phthalate-based plasticizers for PVC [36], yielding exceptional plasticization different building

blocks with particular n properties. As suggested by Bocqué *et al.*, an ideal plasticizer should contain various building moieties, including an aliphatic chain (which act as a spacer), an ester group (which provides a cohesive block), and an aromatic ring which enhances compatibility [37]. Isosorbide diesters ~~cover all these desirable features~~. In this sense, we identified isosorbide as a great precursor candidate for preparing plasticizers. While isosorbide moiety is not an aromatic structure, its heterocyclic nature can still offer great compatibility with the polymeric matrix due to its polar nature. Moreover, the two readily available hydroxyl group make this structure a privileged motif to generate the corresponding diesters, allowing a rational design of the plasticizers with different chain lengths and thus fulfilling most of the features claimed to be needed for good compatibility.. By controlling the alkyl chain length with different fatty acids, it is possible to tailor the desired properties. Isosorbide dioctanoate has shown exceptional plasticization properties on PLA manufactured by thermocompression [38], as well as in PVC [36]. On the other hand, isosorbide dicaprylate has been proposed as secondary plasticizer for PVC [39], while the effect of the alkyl chain on the plasticization efficiency of isosorbide diesters on PVC has been recently studied [40]. This work explores the effect of the chain length of different fatty acids, namely butyric acid (short-chain fatty acid), caprylic acid (medium-chain fatty acid), and palmitic acid (long-chain fatty acid), on the plasticization efficiency of their corresponding isosorbide diesters on fully biobased and biodegradable PLA formulations with improved toughness, thus expanding the potential of isosorbide in designing new environmentally friendly plasticizers for PLA.

2. Experimental.

2.1. Materials.

A PLA commercial grade PURAPOL L130 was obtained from Total Corbion PLA (Gorinchem, The Netherlands). This grade contains a minimum of lactic acid L-isomer content of 99%. Its melt flow index is 16 g/10 min (ISO 1133-A 210 °C/2.16 kg). D-Isosorbide (>98% purity), butyryl chloride (>99%), capryloyl chloride (>99%), and palmitoyl chloride (>98%) were

supplied by Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Solvents and reagents were used as obtained from commercial sources and without purification.

2.2. Synthesis of isosorbide diesters.

This procedure (A) was adapted from a literature report [38]. Isosorbide (80 mmol, 11.8 g) was charged in a two-necked round bottom flask equipped with a stirring bar and a condenser. The system was evacuated under vacuum and backfilled with argon ($\times 3$). Then, dry dichloromethane (125 mL) and triethylamine (240 mmol, 33.8 mL) were added and the mixture was cooled in an ice bath. The corresponding acid chloride (160 mmol) was added dropwise at 0 °C. After addition, the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and then heated to 45 °C for 30 min. The resulting suspension was cooled to room temperature and the mixture was washed with water and brine ($\times 2$). The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered and concentrated in vacuo to afford the crude product. Further purification was achieved by column chromatography over silica gel using mixtures of hexanes and ethyl acetate as eluent.

2.3. Theoretical background of the solubility between PLA and isosorbide diesters.

The theoretical solubility/compatibility of all isosorbide esters with PLA was assessed by the solubility parameter (δ) calculation, using the Van Krevelen & Hoftyzer group contribution method. The solubility parameter includes three different contributions, one corresponding to the dispersive forces, denoted as δ_d , one related to the polar forces, δ_p , and a third component related to the hydrogen bonding interactions, δ_H . The relationship between δ and its contributions is shown in **Eq. 1**.

$$\delta^2 = \delta_d^2 + \delta_p^2 + \delta_H^2 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

The different components can be obtained following **Eq. 2** to **4** [41], with the molar attraction constants of each structural chemical group (i), namely F_{di} , and F_{pi} , for the dispersive

and polar contributions, respectively, and the molar volume, V_m , which results from the ratio of the molecular weight to the density. Regarding to the hydrogen bonding contribution, δ_H , as indicated by Hansen, instead of the molar attraction constants, the cohesive energy, E_{Hi} , is constant for a particular structural group and then, it can be used to determine δ_H as indicated in **Eq. 4**.

$$\delta_d = \frac{\sum F_{di}}{V_m} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\delta_p = \frac{\sqrt{\sum F_{pi}^2}}{V_m} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\delta_H = \sqrt{\frac{\sum E_{Hi}}{V_m}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The solubility region of PLA can be graphically represented by a spherical region in a 3D-space with axes δ_d , δ_p , and δ_H . This spherical region has center coordinates located at δ_{d_PLA} , δ_{p_PLA} , and δ_{H_PLA} , and a radius, R_0 which is characteristic for each polymer. In the case of PLA, $R_0 = 10.7 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ [42]. The solubility of a plasticizer with PLA can be graphically assessed by plotting its δ_{plast} coordinates (δ_{d_plast} , δ_{p_plast} , and δ_{H_plast}). If these coordinates fall into the solubility region of PLA, then good miscibility may be expected. If the δ_{plast} coordinates fall out the solubility region of PLA, then poor miscibility could be expected. This can also numerically be obtained by determining the distance between PLA and the corresponding plasticizer, R_a , as indicated in **Eq. 5**. The constant 4 in the first term, related to the dispersive contribution, δ_d is widely used to obtain spherical solubility regions instead of spheroidal regions, which favour plot representations.

$$R_a = \sqrt{4(\delta_{d_PLA} - \delta_{d_plast})^2 + (\delta_{p_PLA} - \delta_{p_plast})^2 + (\delta_{H_PLA} - \delta_{H_plast})^2} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The suitability of a plasticizer for PLA can be obtained by calculating the relative energy difference (RED), which is the ratio of R_a to R_0 , as indicated in **Eq. 6**. If RED is less than 1 (δ_{plast} inside the solubility region of PLA), then good miscibility is to be expected, and the lower the value of RED, the higher the miscibility. On the contrary, if RED is higher than 1 (δ_{plast} out of the solubility region of PLA), then poor miscibility will be obtained. If $\text{RED} = 1$, the solubility is in the threshold.

$$\text{RED} = \frac{R_a}{R_0} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

2.4. Manufacturing of plasticized PLA samples with isosorbide diesters.

PLA was initially dried at 40 °C for 24 h to remove residual moisture. Different plasticized PLA formulations, containing 10 wt.% and 20 wt.% of each synthesized isosorbide ester were extruded and subsequently injection-moulded for further characterization. The coding includes a number with the wt.%, followed by the abbreviation of the corresponding isosorbide ester, IDB, IDC, IDP, for isosorbide dibutyrate, dicapylate, and dipalmitate, respectively. The plasticization of PLA was carried out in a DSM Xplore MC 15 twin-screw micro compounder from Xplore Instruments BV (Sittard, The Netherlands) at 100 rpm. The mixing process lasted 2 min at 180 °C. Standard samples for further characterization were obtained in a micro injection moulding unit DSM Xplore IM12 from Xplore instruments BV (Sittard, The Netherlands). The injection moulding was carried out at 190 °C using a pressure of 8 bar.

2.5. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) characterization.

The chemical structure of PLA and its plasticized formulations containing different isosorbide diesters was analyzed using a Bruker S.A. Vector 22 spectrometer (Madrid, Spain), equipped with a PIKE MIRacle™ single reflection diamond ATR accessory (Madison, Wisconsin, USA). FTIR analysis was conducted on the samples with 20 scans, at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , covering a wavelength range comprised between 4000 and 600 cm^{-1} .

2.6. Characterization of the synthesized isosorbide diesters.

^1H NMR (400 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz) spectra were recorded on BRUKER AV400 spectrometer in proton coupled mode and in proton decoupled mode, respectively at 20 °C; chemical shifts are given in δ (parts per million) and coupling constants (J) in Hertz. Low-resolution mass spectra (EI) were obtained at 70 eV on an Agilent Technologies GC/MS-8890N, giving fragment ions in m/z with relative intensities (%) in parentheses. High-resolution mass spectra (EI) were recorded at 70 eV on an Agilent 7200 flight (Q-TOF) spectrometer with a Direct Insertion Probe (73DIP-1). Infrared spectra were measured on a Jasco FT/IR-4100 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out on Schleicher & Schuell F1400/LS 254 plates coated with a 0.2 mm layer of silica gel; detection by UV_{254} light. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel 60 of 40-63 mesh.

2.7. Thermal properties of plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters.

The thermal properties of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with isosorbide diesters were obtained by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). DSC tests were carried in a Discovery DSC 25 calorimeter from TA Instruments (New Castle, Delaware, USA) in nitrogen (66 mL/min). Samples were subjected to a dynamic program with three thermal steps: a first heating cycle from 30 °C to 180 °C, a cooling cycle down to 0 °C, and a final second heating cycle from 0 °C to 220 °C. The heating/cooling rate for all the stages was 10 °C/min. Regarding the thermal degradation, it was assessed through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). TGA characterization was carried out in a TG-DSC2 thermobalance from Mettler-Toledo (Columbus, OH, USA). Specimens with an average weight of 10 mg were subjected to a dynamic heating program from 30 °C to 700 °C at 10 °C/min under air atmosphere was used. All tests were performed in triplicate to obtain reliable results.

2.8. Mechanical properties of plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters.

The tensile properties of neat PLA and the plasticized PLA formulations containing different isosorbide diesters, were measured in a universal test machine Duotrac-10/1200 from

SAE Ibertest (Madrid, Spain). The tests were carried out using a load cell of 5 kN, following the indications of ISO 527. All samples were tested at room temperature using a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min. The main tensile properties, name the elongation at break ($\% \epsilon_b$), and the maximum tensile strength (σ_{max}), were averaged. The impact strength was obtained through Charpy impact test on notched samples (“V”-type notch with a radius of 0.5 mm), using a 6-J pendulum from Metrotec S.A. (San Sebastian, Spain), as indicated by ISO 179. Additionally, the Shore D hardness was obtained in a 676-D durometer from J. Bot Instruments (Barcelona, Spain) on samples sizing $80 \times 10 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$, following ISO 868:2003. At least five different samples for each formulation were tested in all three mechanical tests to obtain reliable results.

2.9. Morphology of plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters.

The morphology of the fractured surfaces from Charpy test of neat PLA and its plasticized formulations containing different isosorbide diesters, was obtained by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) in a ZEISS ULTRA 55 microscope from Oxford Instruments (Abingdon, United Kingdom) operated at 2 kV and a working distance of 4 mm. Prior to sample observation by FESEM, they were subjected to a sputtering process with a gold-palladium alloy in a Quorum Technologies, Ltd. (East Sussex, UK) sputter-coater.

2.10. Biodegradation of plasticized PLA with isosorbide esters.

The biodegradation in controlled compost soil of PLA and its plasticized formulations with different isosorbide diesters was evaluated according to ISO 20200. Rectangular samples measuring $10 \times 10 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ were cut, dried at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours, weighed, and then buried in a bioreactor measuring $30 \times 20 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$. The synthetic soil mixture used in the bioreactor contained 40 wt.% sawdust, 10 wt.% corn starch, 30 wt.% rabbit feed, 10 wt.% compost, 5 wt.% sugar, 4 wt.% corn oil, and 1 wt.% urea, combined with distilled water at a 45:55 ratio. The samples underwent aerobic degradation at a constant temperature of $58 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an air-circulating oven for six weeks. At intervals of 1 week, samples were removed from the bioreactor, rinsed with distilled

water, and reweighed to track the degradation progress. To facilitate handling, the samples were placed in textile mesh, which allowed direct contact with the compost soil during degradation while remaining intact for easy removal. After each weight measurement, the specimens were returned to the mesh for continued disintegration. Multiple measurements were taken over the six-week period to monitor the samples' biodegradation profile.

3. Results and discussion.

3.1. Characterization of synthesized isosorbide diesters.

Isosorbide-2,5-dibutyrate (IDB). Obtained from isosorbide and caproyl chloride using general procedure A. Spectroscopic data matched previous literature reports [43]. Yellow oil. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ 5.19 – 5.08 (m, 2H), 4.79 (t, $J = 5.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.44 (dt, $J = 4.7$, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 3.98 – 3.87 (m, 3H), 3.76 (dd, $J = 9.8$, 5.5 Hz, 1H), 2.31 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 2.26 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H), 1.68 – 1.55 (m, 4H), 0.95 – 0.87 (m, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.0, 172.7, 86.0, 80.8, 77.90, 73.8, 73.5, 70.4, 36.0, 35.9, 18.41, 18.38, 13.64, 13.62. IR (ATR): $\nu = 2965, 2937, 2877, 1735, 1461, 1365, 1251, 1170, 1093, 977\text{ cm}^{-1}$. MS (EI): 286 (M^+ , 9), 111 (11), 110 (30), 69 (19), 43 (33).

Isosorbide-2,5-dicaprylate (IDC). Obtained from isosorbide and capryloyl chloride using general procedure A. Spectroscopic data matched previous literature reports [43]. Yellow oil. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.18 (d, $J = 3.5$ Hz, 1H), 5.14 (q, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.81 (t, $J = 5.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.46 (d, $J = 4.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.01 – 3.90 (m, 3H), 3.78 (dd, $J = 9.7$, 5.4 Hz, 1H), 2.35 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 2.29 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 1.69 – 1.54 (m, 4H), 1.35-1.20 (m, 16 H), 0.87 (t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.2, 172.9, 86.0, 80.7, 77.9, 73.7, 73.5, 70.3, 34.2, 34.0, 31.63, 31.61, 29.0, 28.89, 28.86, 24.9, 24.8, 22.6, 14.0. IR (ATR): $\nu = 2954, 2925, 2856, 1739, 1461, 1375, 1160, 1099, 977\text{ cm}^{-1}$. MS (EI): 398 (M^+ , 1), 254 (17), 128 (12), 127 (79), 111 (13), 69 (35), 57 (47), 55 (14), 41 (10).

Isosorbide-2,5-dipalmitate (IDP). Obtained from isosorbide and palmitoyl chloride using general procedure A. Spectroscopic data matched previous literature reports [43]. White solid. m.p. = 68-69 °C (EtOH). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.18 (d, $J = 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 5.14 (q, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1H), 4.82 (t, $J = 5.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.46 (d, $J = 4.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.01 – 3.91 (m, 3H), 3.78 (dd, $J = 9.8$, 5.4 Hz, 1H), 2.36 (dd, $J = 8.2$, 7.0 Hz, 2H), 2.30 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 1.67 – 1.54 (m, 3H), 1.31 – 1.22 (m, 52H), 0.87 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.4, 173.0, 86.1, 80.9, 78.0, 73.9, 73.6, 70.5, 34.3, 34.1, 32.1, 29.83, 29.79, 29.7, 29.6, 29.5, 29.40, 29.36, 29.2, 25.01, 24.98, 22.8, 14.3. IR (ATR): $\nu = 2954, 2917, 2848, 1729, 1467, 1168, 1097, 721\text{ cm}^{-1}$. HRMS (EI) calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{70}\text{O}_6$ (M^+): 622.5172, found: 622.5169.

Figure 1 gathers the ^1H NMR spectra of the synthesized isororbide diesters.

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectra of synthesized isororbide diesters with different chain-length fatty acids, a) isororbide dibutyrate (C4), isororbide dicaprylate (C8), and c) isororbide dipalmitate (C16).

3.2. Theoretical study of the miscibility of PLA with isosorbide esters.

Table 1 gathers the solubility parameters (δ), as well as their contributions, δ_d , δ_p , and δ_H , for PLA and the different isosorbide diesters. As expected, all synthesized isosorbide diesters show a RED value below 1, being representative for good theoretical miscibility with PLA which, in turn, will have a positive effect on the plasticization efficiency of PLA blends with isosorbide diesters. As expected, IDB is the synthesized ester with the lowest molecular weight (286.324 g/mol) due to the esterification with butyric acid, a short length C4 fatty acid. It provides very similar δ_d , and δ_p contribution to δ as PLA, which results in a small distance, Ra.

Table 1. Solubility parameter (δ), and its contributions (δ_d , δ_p , and δ_H) for PLA and isosorbide diesters derived from a short-chain C4 (isosorbide dibutyrate-IDB), a medium-chain C8 (isosorbide dicaprylate-IDC), and a long-chain C16 (isosorbide dipalmitate-IDP) fatty acid.

Code	δ_d (MPa ^{1/2})	δ_p (MPa ^{1/2})	δ_H (MPa ^{1/2})	δ (MPa ^{1/2})	Ra (MPa ^{1/2})	RED
PLA	15.33	8.44	10.98	20.66	-	-
IDB	15.36	3.66	9.04	18.20	5.16	0.48
IDC	15.75	2.38	7.29	17.52	7.14	0.67
IDP	16.13	1.41	5.61	17.13	8.99	0.84

Consequently, the RED value for IDB is remarkably lower than 1, thus suggesting exceptional plasticization. As the fatty acid chain length increases, the number of hydrophobic -CH₂- moieties increases thus leading to increased dispersive contribution, δ_d , while the polar, δ_p and hydrogen bonding, δ_H contributions are remarkably reduced. This increase in hydrophobicity is reflected in larger Ra values, and subsequently, higher RED values. In the case of IDC, which is obtained by esterification with a medium length C8 fatty acid (caprylic acid), the RED value is 0.67 which still indicates good miscibility towards PLA. On the other hand, IDP (obtained by esterification with a C16 fatty acid, namely palmitic acid) shows the highest RED value of 0.84

and, despite it is lower than 1, it is a relatively high value which could indicate limited miscibility. IDP has also a high molecular weight of 622.292 g/mol and a melt temperature of 69.4 °C, which could also affect its miscibility with PLA.

FTIR also shows the presence of the different synthesized isosorbide esters in the PLA mixtures as can be seen in **Figure 2a**. As PLA is the main compound in plasticized formulations its characteristic peak/bands can be clearly seen. It is worthy to note the presence of the peaks at 1751 cm^{-1} and 1180 cm^{-1} which correspond to the stretching vibration of the -C=O , and -C-O contained in the ester groups. Additionally, a peak located at 2994 cm^{-1} is assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the aliphatic C-H [44], with typical band absorption in the 2990 – 2940 cm^{-1} range. The bending (scissoring or deformation) of the methyl group (-CH_3) is observed at 1450 cm^{-1} , while the bending of the C-H can be detected in the 1380 – 1360 cm^{-1} range. It can also be identified the peak corresponding to the crystalline regions of PLA at 868 cm^{-1} . With regard to the plasticized PLA formulations, as PLA is the main component all the above mentioned peaks can also be detected. Nevertheless, some characteristic peaks attributable to isosorbide esters can be detected. The most noticeable change is detected in the 2960 – 2840 cm^{-1} absorption band, related to increasing the number of $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ groups in the synthesized isosorbide diesters ($\text{IDP} > \text{IDC} > \text{IDB}$). In particular, the asymmetric C-H stretching vibration appears at 2921 cm^{-1} , and its peak intensity increases with increasing number of $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ groups. Similar tendency is observed for the symmetric stretching vibration of C-H groups located at 2850 cm^{-1} , with the maximum peak intensity for the plasticized PLA formulation containing 20 wt.% IDP, as expected (**Figure 2b**). Other peaks related to $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ groups include the C-H bending vibrations, namely scissoring, wagging, and twisting, located at 1454 cm^{-1} , 1357 cm^{-1} , and 1265 cm^{-1} , but as PLA also show these peaks, they overlap.

a)

b)

Figure 2. FTIR spectra in different ranges corresponding to neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content.

3.3. Thermal properties of plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is very useful to assess the plasticization efficiency of the synthesized isosorbide diesters (**Figure 3**). Neat PLA has a glass transition

temperature (T_g) of 60.3 °C. It also shows two crystallization processes before melting due to internal rearrangement during heating [45]. The first is a cold crystallization peak (T_{cc}) at 104.8 °C, and the second stands for a pre-melting crystallization peak (T_{pmc}) at 159.9 °C which is related to the α' to α crystalline phase transition [46]. On the other hand, its melting peak temperature (T_m) is 174.4 °C (**Table 2**), which corresponds to the melt temperature of PLA α -crystals. These thermal parameters are typical of semicrystalline PLA [47]. Plasticization efficiency is usually quantified as the ability of a plasticizer to depress the glass transition temperature of the amorphous regions of PLA since plasticizer molecules enter preferentially into the amorphous regions thus leading to an increase in the free volume which, in turns, enhances chain mobility [31]. Zehra-Hasanoglu *et al.* [26], have reported a clear plasticization effect of *Liquidambar orientalis* oil (LO) on PLA that can be corroborated by a decrease in T_g from 58.4 °C down to 41.0 °C with 30 wt.% LO. Yang *et al.* [38], observed the exceptional plasticization efficiency of isosorbide dioctate (SDO) on PLA processed by thermocompression. They observed a decrease in T_g from 60.7 °C (neat PLA) to 32.5 °C for the plasticized formulation containing 20 wt.% SDO. In this work, the effect of the fatty acid chain length is of relevance. As can be seen in **Table 2**, plasticized PLA with 10 wt.% IDB (esterified with a C4 fatty acid) provides a noticeable decrease in T_g down to 47.8 °C thus corroborating its plasticization efficiency. As expected, this decrease in T_g is even more pronounced in formulations containing 20 wt. IDB with a T_g of 36.9 °C. IDC (esterified with a C8 fatty acid) also provides exceptional plasticization efficiency. In fact, the formulation containing 20 wt.% IDC leads to a nadir value of 27.7 °C, which is even lower than that reported by Yang *et al.* [38], thus suggesting the processing methodology also plays a key role in plasticization. It is also worthy to note that plasticization with IDP (esterified with a C16 fatty acid), is not as effective as observed by DSC with a T_g decrease down to values of 56 – 57 °C, which suggests restricted miscibility. Similar findings were reported by Ferri *et al.* [48], in plasticized PLA with maleinized linseed oil (MLO), a maleinized triester of glycerol with C18 fatty acids (oleic, linoleic, and linolenic). They observed plasticizer saturation above 13 wt.% which did not provide additional decrease in T_g nor increase in ductile mechanical properties. Same phenomenon has been observed plasticized PLA formulations containing epoxidized

vegetable oils [49, 50]. DSC thermograms of plasticized PLA with IDP also show a melting peak just above the glass transition. This peak located at 69.4 °C, corresponds to the melting of IDP crystals thus confirming the limited miscibility. This partial miscibility could be ascribed to the high molecular weight of IDP (622.96 g/mol) compared to IDB (286.32 g/mol), and IDC (398.53 g/mol). Usually, good miscibility is obtained with low molecular weight esters such as cinnamates (ranging from 160 to 204 g/mol) [21], terpene-based plasticizers (150 – 252 g/mol) [51, 52], maleates (158 – 258 g/mol) [53, 54]. Nevertheless, the main drawback of these low molecular weight plasticizers is their volatility. Typical ester plasticizers for PLA such as citrates [55], offer good miscibility in a wide composition range. As the molecular weight increases, the miscibility could be affected as it is the case of most oligomeric/polymeric plasticizers [56].

As the chain mobility increases due to plasticization, the crystallization peak temperatures (T_{cc} for the cold crystallization, and T_{pnc} for the pre-melting crystallization) also move towards lower temperatures. Again, the lowest decrease in both T_{cc} and T_{pnc} is obtained with 20 wt.% IDC. This could be related to the higher nucleating capacity of the plasticized PLA formulations compared to unplasticized PLA as suggested Safari *et al.* [57]. With regard to the plasticized PLA formulations with IDP, both T_{cc} and T_{pnc} do not change in a significant way, thus corroborating a limited plasticization efficiency due to partial miscibility. Another important issue that can be assessed by DSC is that most the crystallinity of PLA is developed during the cold crystallization thus suggesting that injection-molded PLA samples with isosorbide diesters develop very low crystallinity during cooling from the melt. These findings agree with those reported by Simmons *et al.* [58], who observed very low degree of crystallinity on PLA (about 5%) after processing by compression moulding. This initial crystallinity was increased up to 15% after annealing at 80 °C, while the addition of different nucleating agents (LAK – potassium salt of 5-dimethyl sulfoisothalate, and TAM – triallyl trimesate), provided a remarkable increase in crystallinity up to values of 50 – 60 °C depending on the nucleant and the annealing temperature.

Figure 3. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) corresponding to the second heating cycled of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content.

The mainly amorphous structure developed by PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with isosorbide diesters was also confirmed by XRD (**Figure 4**). The X-ray diffractogram after processing displays a wide band ranging from 10 to 25°, which is typical of the amorphous regions of PLA. Luna *et al.* [59, 60], observed this behaviour in injection-molded PLA samples without annealing. Even this same XRD pattern was observed for PLA subjected to annealing at 70 °C while annealing at 80 or above led to formation of a crystalline structure with a well-defined XRD diffraction peak at $2\theta = 16.79^\circ$ which corresponds to the (200) and (110) diffraction planes of α -type crystals, and a very small peak at $2\theta = 18.98^\circ$ which corresponds to the (203) plane of the α -phase. None of these peaks can be seen in **Figure 4**, except for the plasticized PLA formulation containing 20 wt.% IDB with a clear peak arising at $2\theta = 16.74^\circ$, and a peak with less intensity for the plasticized PLA formulation with 10 wt.% IDB. This suggests the diester with the shortest fatty acid (C4) used in this study, promotes a slight increase in crystallinity during cooling from the melt, while diesters with longer fatty acids (C8, and C16), do not provide increased

crystallinity during cooling. Similar findings have been reported by Gomez-Caturla *et al.* [24], in plasticized PLA formulations with terpenoid-based plasticizers. Interestingly, plasticized PLA formulations with 10, and 20 wt.% IDP show clear XRD peaks at $2\theta = 7.7^\circ$, 20.3° , 22.1° , and 23.9° which are related to immiscible IDP crystals as suggested by DSC.

Figure 4. X-ray diffraction patterns corresponding to neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content.

Regarding the thermal degradation, **Figure 5** shows the mass loss (**Figure 5a**), and the first derivative of the mass loss, DTG (**Figure 5b**) for all PLA-based formulations, while the main thermal degradation parameters are gathered in **Table 2**. PLA degradation takes place in a single-step process characterized by an onset (temperature at which a 5 wt.% mass loss occurs, or T_5) of 332.6°C , and a maximum degradation rate temperature (T_{max}) of 382.2°C . With regard to the thermal degradation profile of the plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters, the effect of the fatty acid length is evident. The molecular weight of the synthesized isosorbide esters follow this tendency: IDB (286.32 g/mol) < IDC (398.53 g/mol) < IDP (622.96 g/mol). As low molecular weight compounds are, in general, more volatile, than high molecular weight compounds, the fatty acid length influences the main thermal degradation parameters. This is important since at

moderate temperatures this phenomenon could lead to plasticizer removal during processing, thus limiting its efficiency. As can be seen in **Table 2**, the onset degradation temperature (T_5) of the plasticized PLA with 10, and 20 wt.% IDB reaches the lowest values of 255.3 °C, and 240.7 °C, respectively. The T_5 for IDC, and IDP-plasticized PLA formulations is higher, as expected, due to their higher molecular weight compared to IDB. These findings are very important since they mean the plasticizers is not removed during the conventional processing temperature range of PLA around 190 °C. Similar findings have been reported by Brdlík *et al.* [61], in plasticized PLA with PEG (380 - 420 g/mol), ATBC (402 g/mol), and two plasticizers derived from dicarboxylic acids, namely MC 2179 (1250 g/mol), and MC 2192 (4236 g/mol). As the molecular weight of the employed plasticizer increases, the T_5 decrease is lower. On the other hand, as described by Llanes *et al.* [54], in plasticized PLA with dibutyl maleate (DBM), and dibutyl fumarate (DBF), even some plasticizer removal occurs during processing (14.3 to 29.0%) due to the low molecular weight of both DBM, and DBF, the plasticization efficiency is maintained, with exceptional mechanical ductile properties and a noticeable decrease in T_g . Therefore, TGA results on plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters indicates no plasticizer loss during processing, which is a key feature. Regarding the maximum degradation rate temperature (T_{max}), as it is related to the thermal degradation of the PLA backbone, it does not change in a remarkable way.

a)

b)

Figure 5. Thermal degradation profiles corresponding to neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content, a) mass loss vs temperature, and b) first derivative (DTG) vs temperature.

Table 2. Main thermal parameters of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content obtained by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and thermogravimetry (TGA).

Code	DSC thermal parameters				TGA thermal parameters		
	T _g (°C)	T _{cc} (°C)	T _{pmc} (°C)	T _m (°C)	T ₅ (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T ₉₅ (°C)
PLA	60.3 ± 0.3	104.8 ± 0.6	159.9 ± 0.8	174.4 ± 0.6	332.6	382.2	392.5
PLA/10IDB	47.8 ± 0.6	94.1 ± 0.9	-	168.4 ± 0.9	255.3	383.2	394.4
PLA/10IDC	47.2 ± 0.7	91.6 ± 0.9	150.3 ± 2.2	169.8 ± 0.7	314.2	384.2	393.5
PLA/10IDP	57.6 ± 0.4	96.8 ± 1.0	155.7 ± 1.1	165.7 ± 0.9	319.7	374.8	385.6
PLA/20IDB	36.9 ± 0.8	81.6 ± 1.0	-	164.3 ± 0.5	240.7	385.6	394.3
PLA/20IDC	27.7 ± 1.1	73.7 ± 0.8	143.1 ± 1.8	166.2 ± 0.9	294.7	384.3	391.6
PLA/20IDP	56.2 ± 0.6	102.2 ± 0.9	154.8 ± 1.2	170.7 ± 1.1	306.7	376.1	386.3

3.4. Mechanical properties of plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters.

The plasticizing efficiency of the synthesized isosorbide diesters with different fatty acid chain length was also assessed by characterization of tensile properties, impact strength and Shore D hardness. **Table 3** gathers the main mechanical properties obtained by tensile, impact and hardness tests. Neat PLA is characterized by a tensile strength of 67.7 MPa with a relative low elongation at break of 12.8% which, in turn, is responsible for its intrinsic brittleness. The addition of 10 wt.% IDB or 10 wt.% IDC does not lead to a noticeable increase in ductile properties while the tensile strength decreases by 15 – 17 MPa. It has been reported that the plasticization mechanisms need a certain threshold to be triggered. Gomez-Caturla *et al.* [62], have observed this phenomenon in plasticized PLA with esters of tartaric acid. At a plasticizer content of 10 wt.% the elongation at break (8.2%) was even lower than neat PLA (11.3%), while at a plasticizer content of 20 wt.%, the elongation increased dramatically up to 567.6%. Similar findings were reported by Barandiaran *et al.* [21], in plasticized PLA with esters of cinnamic acid. Murariu *et al.* [63], have reported the relevance of the threshold composition to reach plasticization in PLA. While PLA showed an elongation at break of 11%, they observed equal (11%) or lower (8%)

elongation at break values with 10 wt.% of acetyl tributyl citrate (TBAC), or glyceryl triacetate (GTA), respectively. Surprisingly, the elongation at break increased up to 221% and 223% with 20 wt.% TBAC, or GTA, respectively. Recently, Sun *et al.* [25], have shown that this threshold highly depends on the chemical structure of the proposed plasticizer. They found this threshold to be 10 wt.% for glyceryl tributyrate, while this increased to 20 wt.% for glyceryl triacetate (triacetine), or triethyl citrate. In this work, the plasticization efficiency of isosorbide diesters of short or medium-length (C4-C8) fatty acids is impressive at a concentration of 20 wt.% with elongation at break values of 529.1%, and 342.0% for plasticized PLA formulations containing IDB, or IDC, respectively (**Figure 6**). Another interesting issue that can be seen in **Figure 6** is that neat PLA and plasticized formulations with IDB, and IDC are transparent (even the highly elongated specimens after the tensile test), which is compatible with the previous observations of a mainly amorphous state. On the other hand, plasticized samples with IDP are opaque (grey) since due to the partial miscibility, IDP crystals are formed at 69.4 °C during the cooling from the melt, and this plays a key role in opacity. These results are comparable, or even superior to most typical PLA plasticizers such as citrate esters, oligomers of lactic acid, polyethylene glycol (PEG) or polypropylene glycol (PPG), or epoxidized vegetable oils, among others [55]. Regarding the efficiency of isosorbide diester with long fatty acid (C16), due to the partial miscibility, an increase in ductile properties can be seen, but this is less pronounced than esters containing C4 and C8 fatty acids. The low impact strength is another drawback of PLA also contributing to its brittleness. In a similar way to elongation at break, the addition of 10 wt.% IDB or IDC, leads to slightly lower impact strength values of 0.17 – 0.18 kJ/m², while this is notably improved with 20 wt.% IDB, or IDC, reaching impact strength values of 0.38 kJ/m², and 0.59 kJ/m², respectively. IDP offers a different behaviour, probably due to phase separation. Anyway, IDP also provides increased impact strength thus confirming that, even phase separation can occur, mechanical properties are improved. As expected, the Shore D hardness of PLA is barely changed by both IDB and IDC at 10 wt.% concentration, while a decrease of 8 – 10 units is observed at a concentration of 20 wt.% these two plasticizers.

Table 3. Mechanical properties of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content obtained by tensile, impact and hardness tests.

Code	Tensile strength, σ_{\max} (MPa)	Elongation at break, $\% \epsilon_b$	Impact strength (kJ/m ²)	Shore D hardness
PLA	67.7 ± 1.0	12.8 ± 1.6	0.23 ± 0.04	81.2 ± 0.8
PLA/10IDB	52.5 ± 1.0	13.8 ± 1.6	0.17 ± 0.02	81.3 ± 0.8
PLA/10IDC	50.3 ± 2.0	16.1 ± 3.7	0.18 ± 0.01	80.7 ± 1.6
PLA/10IDP	43.4 ± 5.4	47.9 ± 4.2	0.38 ± 0.04	76.0 ± 1.1
PLA/20IDB	26.1 ± 1.4	529.1 ± 31.8	0.59 ± 0.05	71.4 ± 1.5
PLA/20IDC	27.6 ± 3.0	342.0 ± 46.2	0.44 ± 0.02	74.2 ± 1.1
PLA/20IDP	33.2 ± 3.3	87.7 ± 5.6	0.35 ± 0.04	72.5 ± 1.9

Figure 6. Images of the fractured specimens of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content, after tensile tests.

The FESEM images of the fractured samples after impact tests (**Figure 7**) gives support to the previous findings. As can be seen in **Figure 7a**, neat PLA shows a rather brittle fracture characterized by flat surfaces and low roughness as typical brittle polymers [64]. Plasticization with IDB gives a homogeneous phase which is representative for good miscibility, as the theoretical study suggested. IDP has a RED value of 0.48 with regard to PLA, and this is consistent with good miscibility. On the other hand, some evidences of the plastic deformation can be seen on the form of wavy regions and presence of filaments which indicate plastic deformation [65]. As expected, these signs are clearly seen in the plasticized PLA with 20 wt.% IDB (**Figure 7c**), with an elongation at break of 529.1%, while these wavy regions are less intense in the plasticized formulation containing 10 wt.% IDB, with just 13.8% elongation at break. Similar behaviour can be seen in plasticized PLA formulations with IDC. Samples with 10 wt.% IDC (**Figure 7d**) shows a rather brittle fracture surface (smooth and flat regions combined with scarce wavy regions and filaments) according to the low elongation at break of 16.1% compared to neat PLA (12.8%). On the other hand, the sample containing 20 wt.% IDC shows a ductile fracture morphology with a wrinkled topography as a result of the micro deformations during fracture (**Figure 7e**). Regarding plasticized formulations with IDP, a clear phase separation phenomenon can be observed. Despite there is partial miscibility and some signs of plastic deformation can be seen (filaments and rough surface), it is worthy to note a biphasic structure with a PLA-rich matrix and spherical IDP particles/crystals finely embedded in the polymeric matrix (**Figure 7f and 7g**). These IDP spherical particles are larger with increasing the IDP content. These morphology is consistent with the previous findings and the theoretical miscibility study. As it has been shown, DSC results revealed a slight decrease in T_g due to slight miscibility, and a clear melt peak at 69.4 °C corresponding to IDP crystals.

Figure 7. FESEM images (2000×) of the fractured specimens (impact test) of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content, a) PLA, b) PLA/10IDB, c) PLA/20IDB, d) PLA/10IDC, e) PLA/20IDC, f) PLA/10IDP, and g) PLA/20IDP.

The theoretical study revealed a RED of 0.84 with regard to PLA and, despite RED is less than 1, the high hydrophobicity provided by palmitic acid, results in phase separation. This

phenomenon has been observed in plasticized PLA systems with high molecular weight compounds. Mena-Prado *et al.* [66], have reported phase separation in PLA plasticized with CITREM (citric acid esters of mono- and diglycerides). Nevertheless, despite phase separation occurs, they observed increased elongation at break up to 42.5% and, despite the CITREM domains can act as stress concentrators, they provide shear-induced plastic deformation that results in improved toughness, as observed in this study, thus leading to interesting features to obtain tough PLA without reducing its T_g . Garcia-Garcia *et al.* [67], also observed phase separation in plasticized PLA with epoxidized karanja oil above 5 wt.%, and FESEM study corroborated this by presence of spherical regions related to excess plasticizer. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fatty acid chain length plays a key role in miscibility. Isosorbide esters with short-medium length (C4, and C8), lead to exceptional miscibility, while its esters with a long fatty acid (C16), leads to phase separation which, in turn, could play a key role in improving toughness.

3.5. Disintegration in compost soil of plasticized PLA with isosorbide diesters

Despite the technical feasibility of isosorbide diesters provide in PLA plasticization, environmental issues related to biodegradation must also be taken into account, to ensure low environmental impact. In this case, isosorbide diesters are considered as green plasticizers because they come from renewable resources, but it is also important to assess their effect on disintegration in compost soil, so they fulfil the “double green” criteria from an environmental stand point, both at the start of the life cycle (biobased), and at the end of the life cycle (biodegradable or disintegrable in compost soil) [68], as well as the technical features that plasticizers must provide. **Figure 8** gathers the visual evolution of the disintegration of plasticized PLA formulations with isosorbide diesters with time, while **Figure 9** shows the evolution of the mass loss during this test. PLA disintegrates in almost 35 days. Regarding the effect of isosorbide diesters, it can be seen that isosorbide diesters with short (C4), and medium-length (C8) fatty acids, show higher disintegration rate than PLA (slightly faster). After an incubation time of 7 days, disintegration proceeds faster than in neat PLA. In fact, the mass loss is <80% after 21 days,

while PLA needs 35 days to reach similar disintegration. Moreover, the isosorbide diester with medium-length fatty acid (C8), gives the fastest disintegration rate as seen in **Figure 9**. It is important to bear in mind that biodegradation processes carried by microorganisms have more tendency to occur in the amorphous regions and, as we have shown previously, the injection-molded samples are mainly amorphous as this PLA grade cannot develop high crystallinity during the cooling from the melt. In general, as the fatty acid chain length increases, the disintegration becomes slower [69], but crystallinity is also plays an important role in disintegration as crystalline regions are less accessible than amorphous regions [70]. In the case of plasticized PLA with IDB, despite IDB contains short-length fatty acids (C4) and is more sensitive to biodegradation due to the short length fatty acid chains [71], as XRD has revealed, they offer slightly higher crystallinity that IDC, and IDP-plasticized PLA samples, thus, the overall effect on biodegradation is a disintegration rate in-between that observe for IDC-plasticized materials, and neat PLA. The maximum degradation rate is obtained with IDC, which contains medium-length (C8) fatty acids, with excellent combination of low crystallinity and balanced hydrocarbon backbone length.

Figure 8. Visual appearance of neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type and content during the disintegration in controlled compost soil test.

Figure 9. Mass loss evolution with incubation time corresponding to neat PLA and plasticized PLA formulations with varying isosorbide diester type.

4. Conclusions.

The plasticization efficiency of various isosorbide diesters with fatty acids of different chain length, namely isosorbide dibutyrate (IDB), with short-chain fatty acid-C4, isosorbide dicaprylate (IDC), with medium-chain fatty acid-C8, and isosorbide dipalmitate (IDP) with high-chain fatty acid-C16. Isosorbide esters with short (C4) and medium-chain (C8) fatty acids show exceptional miscibility with PLA from a theoretical point of view. Moreover, this miscibility has been corroborated by a noticeable decrease in T_g , and cold crystallization peak temperature. FESEM has also revealed monophasic structure with clear signs of plastic deformation at a concentration of 20 wt.% both IDB, and IDC. In accordance to the T_g depression from 60.3 °C (neat PLA) to 36.9 °C (PLA/20IDB) and 27.7 °C (PLA/20IDC), both IDP and IDC provided a dramatic increase in elongation at break from 12.8% up to 529.1% and 342.0% at a concentration of 20 wt.% thus showing the exceptional plasticization efficiency they provide to PLA. Regarding IDP-plasticized PLA formulations, it is worthy to note the partial miscibility of IDP with PLA due to presence of long-chain (C16) fatty acid, which was confirmed by a melting peak at 69.4 °C

corresponding to IDP crystals, and a dual-phase morphology observed by FESEM. This partial miscibility led to moderate decrease in T_g , with subsequent modest increase in elongation at break but high improvement in impact strength. This dual phase structure arises as a technical solution to improve impact strength and ductile properties of PLA without decreasing T_g . The fatty acid chain-length has also great influence on biodegradation or disintegration in compost soil. Two main phenomenon govern the disintegration in compost soil. On the one hand, the crystallinity, and the second one, the free volume. Introduction of isosorbide diesters do not lead to a crystalline structure thus favoring disintegration. On the other hand, all three isosorbide diesters increase the free volume since they place between PLA polymer chains. The fatty acid chain length also plays a key role in biodegradation. The maximum disintegration rate has been observed in IDC-plasticized PLA formulations due to a combination of a predominantly amorphous structure, and medium-chain length alkyl. All in all, isosorbide diesters arise as a “double green” plasticizers for PLA since they fulfil two relevant environmental criteria. On the one hand, these plasticizers are obtained from renewable resources and, on the second hand, they positively contribute to disintegration in compost soil, thus widening the industrial applications of PLA with improved ductile properties.

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